

Generation of Free Carriers in MoSe₂ Monolayers Via Energy Transfer from CsPbBr₃ Nanocrystals

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Transition metal dichalcogenide (TMDCs) monolayers make an excellent component in optoelectronic devices such as photodetectors and phototransistors. Selenide-based TMDCs, specifically molybdenum diselenide (MoSe₂) monolayers with low defect densities, show much faster photoresponses compared to their sulfide counterpart. However, the typically low absorption of the atomically thin MoSe₂ monolayer and high exciton binding energy limit the photogeneration of charge carriers. Yet, integration of light-harvesting materials with TMDCs can produce increased photocurrents via energy transfer. In this article, it is demonstrated that the interaction of cesium lead bromide (CsPbBr₃) nanocrystals with MoSe₂ monolayers results into an energy transfer efficiency of over 86%, as ascertained from the quenching and decay dynamics of the CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals emission. Notably, the increase in the MoSe₂ monolayer emission in the heterostructure accounts only for 33% of the transferred energy. It is found that part of the excess energy generates directly free carriers in the MoSe₂ monolayer, as a result of the transfer of energy into the exciton continuum. The efficiency of the heterostructure via enhanced photocurrents with respect to the single material unit is proven. These results demonstrate a viable route to overcome the high exciton binding energy typical for TMDCs, as such having an impact on optoelectronic processes that rely on efficient exciton dissociation.

1. Introduction

The family of transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDCs) crystals is a class of van der Waals materials with a layered structure.^[1] They are an attractive component in semiconductor devices thanks to their outstanding electronic, mechanical, optical, thermal, and chemical properties at the monolayer level.^[2–6] They also show excellent in-plane carrier mobility, high quantum efficiency, and the indirect to direct bandgap crossover approaching the monolayer thickness, which favors light-matter interaction.^[1,7,8] In particular, two-dimensional (2D) molybdenum diselenide (MoSe₂) shows a bandgap (E_g) of ≈ 1.55 eV, which is close to the optimal bandgap value of single-junction solar cells and photo-electrochemical devices.^[9,10] For these reasons, MoSe₂ is a competitive candidate for applications in electronics and photonics. However, the realization of MoSe₂-based optoelectronic devices is limited by their weak optical absorption

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in the visible spectra range and consequently low generation of carriers in the atomically thin layer.^[11,12] Additionally, quantum confinement effects and reduced Coulomb screening give rise to large exciton binding energies of around 100 meV, preventing the spontaneous or thermally induced dissociation of the exciton into free charges.^[13] This effect is detrimental for various optoelectronic applications, such as the generation of photocurrent, which rely on the efficient dissociation of excitons.^[13]

The coupling of light-harvesting materials that can transfer the absorbed light energy to the TMDC crystals, represents an interesting route to overcome the abovementioned limitations. The key process involved in finding suitable materials for the design and manufacture of such hybrid optoelectronic devices is the efficient transfer of energy and/or charge at the interface. Several low-dimensional light-harvesting materials such as colloidal quantum dots, perovskites, nanowires, and other layered materials have been integrated with TMDCs.^[14–19] Among them, cesium lead bromide (CsPbBr₃) nanocrystals represent an emerging class of materials with excellent visible light absorption, high defect tolerance, long carrier diffusion length, and size-dependent electronic properties, showing an E_g of ≈ 2.4 eV.^[16] In fact, in initial works, the interaction between CsPbBr₃ and Se-based TMDCs was studied. For example, Zhang et al.^[14] demonstrated near-unity energy transfer efficiency between bulk CsPbBr₃ and WSe₂ and Hassan et al.^[20] reported an enhanced photocurrent in a CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals and MoSe₂ nanosheets hybrid.

In this article, we show that the coupling of colloidal CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals with MoSe₂ monolayers results in an energy transfer efficiency of more than 86%, supported by optical measurements of emission quenching/enhancement and carrier lifetime. Importantly, we found that the transferred energy from CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals to MoSe₂ monolayers results in the direct generation of free carriers in MoSe₂ monolayers, with a 33% increase in the free carrier density compared to pristine MoSe₂ monolayers. Only a fraction of the generated free carriers recombines radiatively. This indicates a novel route to overcome the strong exciton binding energy of monolayer TMDCs by exploiting energy transfer to the exciton continuum of the TMDC. Our findings are supported by an order of magnitude (nA to sub- μ A) increase in the photocurrent of the CsPbBr₃/MoSe₂ heterostructure with respect to the pristine MoSe₂ monolayers.

2. Results and Discussion

We prepared stable CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals (P-NCs) passivated with didodecyldimethylammonium bromide (DDAB) as a ligand using methods previously developed in our groups (also described in the Methods section in the Supporting Information).^[21,22] Figure 1a shows the scanning electron microscope (SEM) image of a uniform single layer of P-NCs on a Si/SiO₂ substrate. As synthesized P-NCs have a size distribution of $\approx 7.2 \pm 0.8$ nm (transmission electron microscope (TEM) image and size

Figure 1. a) Scanning electron microscope (SEM) image of uniform P-NCs on Si/SiO₂ substrate. b) Optical micrograph of exfoliated ML-MoSe₂. c) Absorption spectra (in dashed curve) of P-NC (green), ML-MoSe₂ (red) and PL spectra (solid curve) of P-NC (green), ML-MoSe₂ (red), Schematic of type I band alignment of P-NC and ML-MoSe₂ shown in inset.

distribution analysis shown in Figure S1a,b). The MoSe₂ monolayers (ML-MoSe₂) were prepared using the Au-assisted exfoliation technique (see Methods in Supporting Information), which enables the fabrication of large-area samples ranging from a few to hundreds of micrometers.^[23–25] The optical micrograph of an exfoliated monolayer is shown in Figure 1b. As-synthesized colloidal P-NC films were fabricated via spin coating, resulting in nearly monolayer films, as characterized by SEM (Figure 1a). We first characterized the bare P-NC films using optical absorption and photoluminescence spectroscopy. The P-NCs exhibit an exciton peak absorption at 505 nm and an emission maximum at 515 nm (Figure 1c). Emission at 515 nm is close to the bulk CsPbBr₃ emission wavelength (maximum at 525 nm)^[26] indicating weak confinement in P-NCs. The absorption spectrum of ML-MoSe₂ shown in Figure 1c was calculated using Beer–Lambert law from the absorption coefficient spectrum taken from the literature.^[27] The PL spectrum of ML-MoSe₂ was measured in a μ -PL system and is displayed in Figure 1c, evidencing a maximum PL around 800 nm. An overlap of the emission of the P-NC and the absorption of ML-MoSe₂ is observed, which represents a prerequisite for efficient energy transfer between P-NC and ML-MoSe₂ crystals. The valence band maximum energy (E_{VBM}) of -5.6 eV and the conduction band minimum energy (E_{CBM}) of -3.1 eV of the P-NCs were taken from a previous report for the same type of P-NCs.^[21] The calculated E_{VBM} and E_{CBM} of -3.9 and -5.2 eV of ML-MoSe₂ were taken from a previous report.^[28] Together, P-NC and ML-MoSe₂ form a type I band alignment, as depicted in Figure 1c.

The fabrication of the CsPbBr₃/MoSe₂ heterostructure (HET) was carried out via spin-coating of the P-NCs on top of the ML-MoSe₂. Upon spin coating, the P-NCs form a monolayer on top of both, substrate and ML-MoSe₂, as shown in the schematic in Figure 2a. This is confirmed by SEM, where a monolayer of P-NCs (solution concentration: 2 mg mL⁻¹) is observed on top of ML-MoSe₂ and the substrate, as shown in Figure 2b. Figure 2c shows a fluorescence microscopy image of P-NC emission intensity distribution in the HET acquired using a 400 nm laser excitation and a detection range of 480–550 nm. Notably, the P-NCs emission intensity on the ML-MoSe₂ (optical micrograph shown in Figure 1b) was significantly quenched compared to the bare P-NC emission on the substrate suggesting energy transfer from the P-NCs to the ML-MoSe₂.

To better quantify the emission characteristics and understand the physical origin of the quenching, we performed μ -PL spectroscopy (laser spot size of 1.7 μm) on P-NCs deposited on the ML-MoSe₂ (referred as HET) and on the substrate

only (P-NC). Figure 3a shows the steady-state μ -PL spectrum of P-NCs emission on substrate (in green) and the P-NCs emission in the HET (in black). Upon excitation with a 400 nm laser, we see PL from P-NCs around 515 nm, which gets quenched significantly when the P-NCs are placed on ML-MoSe₂. The ML-MoSe₂ emission instead is enhanced in the case of HET as shown in Figure 3b (ML-MoSe₂ emission spectrum on substrate in red and in HET in black). To be able to separate the monolayer ML-MoSe₂ PL from the perovskite P-NC PL, the former being orders of magnitude smaller, we diluted the P-NC film coupled to the ML-MoSe₂. We used 50 times diluted P-NCs sample and identified a sparse distribution of P-NCs on the substrate as well as on the ML-MoSe₂ (SEM image is given in Figure S2, Supporting Information). The corresponding absorption spectrum is given in Figure S3, Supporting Information. These three experimental observations, namely the overlapping of the P-NCs emission with the optical absorption of ML-MoSe₂ (Figure 1c), the quenching of the PL of P-NCs in the HET (Figure 3a), and the simultaneous enhancement in the ML-MoSe₂ PL (Figure 3b), suggest an energy transfer from the P-NCs to the ML-MoSe₂. The efficiency of energy transfer in the HET can be quantified from both donor (P-NC) quenching and acceptor (ML-MoSe₂) enhancement (statistics to the quantification are found in Figure S4, Supporting Information). If the energy transfer in the HET is the only process involved in the relaxation of the excited carriers besides spontaneous emission, we can calculate the efficiency from P-NC quenching using the following equation^[29]:

$$\phi_{\text{ET}} = 1 - \frac{A_{\text{P-NC}}(\lambda_{\text{exc}})}{A_{\text{HET}}(\lambda_{\text{exc}}) - A_{\text{ML-MoSe}_2}(\lambda_{\text{exc}})} \cdot \frac{I_{\text{P-NC}}}{I_{\text{P-NC}}^0} = 1 - \frac{I_{\text{P-NC}}}{I_{\text{P-NC}}^0} \quad (1)$$

where ϕ_{ET} is the efficiency of energy transfer (ET), and $A_{\text{P-NC}}(\lambda_{\text{exc}})$, $A_{\text{HET}}(\lambda_{\text{exc}})$, $A_{\text{ML-MoSe}_2}(\lambda_{\text{exc}})$ are the absorbance of the P-NCs, the HET and the ML-MoSe₂ at the excitation wavelength (400 nm), respectively. The values of $I_{\text{P-NC}}^0$ and $I_{\text{P-NC}}$ are the integrated intensities of P-NC emission on the substrate and in the case of HET, respectively. We measured the value of $A_{\text{P-NC}}(\lambda_{\text{exc}})$ by spin-coating a uniform layer of P-NCs on fused silica, reproducing the same process used for the HET formation with the ML-MoSe₂ (absorbance spectrum shown in Figure 1c in dashed green). The absorbance of the ML-MoSe₂ ($A_{\text{ML-MoSe}_2}(\lambda_{\text{exc}})$), at the excitation wavelength was calculated to be 0.245 using the Beer–Lambert law and the absorption coefficient taken from the literature.^[27] Due to the presence of an isolating barrier (ligand: DDAB) between P-NCs and ML-MoSe₂

Figure 2. a) Schematic of the arrangement of P-NCs on ML-MoSe₂ and the substrate. b) SEM image of a film of P-NCs on ML-MoSe₂, bulk MoSe₂, and the Si/SiO₂ substrate. c) Confocal PL (480–550 nm) image of P-NCs on ML-MoSe₂ (dark region) and on Si/SiO₂ substrate (bright green emission).

Figure 3. a) PL spectra of P-NCs in the HET (black) and on the substrate (green) excited with a 400 nm laser with an excitation power of 1 μ W and 1s integration time. b) PL spectra of ML-MoSe₂ in the HET (black) and without P-NCs (red) excited with 400 nm laser with an excitation power of 60 μ W and 10 s integration time. Both spectra have been deconvoluted into their contribution of the exciton (X_0 , blue) and trion (X_T , orange) PL. c) PL emission decay of the P-NCs in the HET (black) and on the substrate (green). d) Schematic model depicting the major photoinduced processes in the single components (left) of CsPbBr₃ NCs (green) and MoSe₂ (red) and the HET (right). The grey shaded area illustrates the DDAB ligands that physically separate the two domains of the HET. The change in arrows' weight indicates the observed emission quenching and enhancement.

it is safe to assume zero ground state interaction, hence, $A_{\text{HET}}(\lambda_{\text{exc}})$ can be written as the sum of the absorbance of the individual materials.^[30,31] All the values used in this calculation are shown in Table S1, Supporting Information. With this assumption, we can simplify Equation 1 in terms of integrated PL intensities of P-NCs on and off (substrate only) the HET.^[32] Applying the equation for the PL spectra of P-NC emission, we calculate the ET efficiency to be 86%.

We further quantify the rate and efficiency of the exciton energy transfer from time-resolved μ -PL spectroscopy of P-NC emission on and off the HET. A 400 nm pulsed laser with a pulse width of 49.7 ps and a repetition rate of 10 MHz was used for excitation and P-NC PL was detected using an avalanche photo-diode (APD) connected to a time-correlated single-photon counting (TCSPC) system. The average PL lifetime in the case of ML-MoSe₂ is in the range of a few picoseconds, which is below the resolution of the TCSPC. Therefore, we calculated the rates from the P-NCs PL decay alone. Figure 3c shows the PL decay of P-NCs on the substrate (green, and the fit in dashed yellow) and in the HET (black, and the fit in dashed red). The P-NCs emission is characterized by a faster decay on the HET compared to the P-NCs on the substrate. The P-NCs emission on the substrate has a biexponential decay (see Equation S1, Supporting Information) with rates (K_1 and K_2) of $0.8 \times 10^9 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $0.29 \times 10^9 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and amplitudes of 0.51 and 0.49, respectively (the respective time constants are given in Table S3, Supporting Information and Section 2, Supporting Information). In comparison, the PL decay of the P-NCs on the

HET displays a monoexponential (see Equation S3, Supporting Information) behavior, with a rate (K) of $4.16 \times 10^9 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and a lifetime of 0.24 ns. Since the decay of HET is close to the instrument response function of the system, the convoluted fit could still overestimate the time constant (τ_{HET}) and underestimate the energy transfer rate and efficiency. Therefore the estimated energy transfer rate and efficiency provide us with a lower limit and the real values are expected to be even larger. We calculate the amplitude average lifetime from the P-NCs PL decay on the substrate to be 2.8 ns (see Equation S2, Supporting Information).^[33] There is an order of magnitude decrease in the excited state lifetime of the P-NCs when it is part of the HET. We then calculate the rate (K_{ET}) and the efficiency of ET using Equations 2 and 3:

$$K_{\text{ET}} = \frac{1}{\tau_{\text{HET}}} - \frac{1}{\tau_{\text{P-NC}}} \quad (2)$$

$$\phi_{\text{ET}} = 1 - \frac{\tau_{\text{HET}}}{\tau_{\text{P-NC}}} \quad (3)$$

Where $\tau_{\text{P-NC}}$ is the average lifetime of P-NC PL on the substrate and τ_{HET} is the average lifetime of P-NCs PL on the HET. We apply these formulae and calculate the ET rate to be $3.8 \times 10^9 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and ϕ_{ET} to be $\approx 92\%$. Notably, while the P-NC PL decay off the HET shows two different recombination rates, the P-NC emission on the HET shows a mono-exponential decay. The biexponential nature of the P-NC PL decay off the

HET is typical for this type of material and is usually assigned to different defect-mediated recombination mechanisms.^[34,35] The mono-exponential decay in the HET instead indicates a dominant ET, i.e., most of the excited state charge carriers irrespective of their origin lose their energy via the energy transfer process.

The efficiency of energy transfer can also be calculated from the acceptor PL. For an acceptor system with unity PL quantum yield, almost all the transferred energy should result in the enhancement of the acceptor PL. Therefore, the efficiency calculated from the enhancement should match the quenching efficiency of the donor. Using Equation 4, we calculate the ET efficiency from ML-MoSe₂ PL enhancement:

$$\phi_{\text{ET}} = \frac{A_{\text{ML-MoSe}_2}(\lambda_{\text{exc}})}{A_{\text{HET}}(\lambda_{\text{exc}}) - A_{\text{ML-MoSe}_2}(\lambda_{\text{exc}})} \left(\frac{I_{\text{ML-MoSe}_2}}{I_{\text{ML-MoSe}_2}^0} - 1 \right) \quad (4)$$

where $I_{\text{ML-MoSe}_2}^0$ and $I_{\text{ML-MoSe}_2}$ are the integrated PL intensities of ML-MoSe₂ off and on the HET respectively.^[29] The value of $A_{\text{P-NC}}$ in the HET is taken from the absorption spectrum of the diluted NC film in Figure S3, Supporting Information. All the values used in this calculation are shown in Table S2, supporting information. Applying Equation 4, we calculate the ET efficiency to be 33%, implying an increased number of excitons in ML-MoSe₂. We want to remark that the quenching of P-NC PL, faster PL decay of P-NC, and the enhancement of ML-MoSe₂ PL are most probably a result of the Förster resonance energy transfer (FRET), due to the significant overlap in the emission of the donor (P-NC) and absorption of the acceptor (ML-MoSe₂) and the large separation distance between both due to the organic ligand (DDAB) passivation of the P-NC. A direct charge transfer from P-NC and ML-MoSe₂ is improbable due to the spatial barriers in the form of the DDAB.^[36–38]

Figure 3d shows the two-particle energy level model that summarizes the results thus far: upon optical excitation of the P-NCs alone, we observe a strong PL with two different excited state populations that recombines at different rates. In the heterostructure, on the other hand, we observe ≈86% of exciton energy from P-NCs being transferred to the ML-MoSe₂. The nonradiative energy transfer reduces the PL lifetime of P-NC in the heterostructure to a fast monoexponential decay. The calculated efficiency from time-resolved data of 92% agrees well with the PL quenching data. The ET efficiency of 33% calculated from the enhancement of ML-MoSe₂ PL represents the increase in the number of excitons in ML-MoSe₂. Efficient quenching from P-NCs PL is evidence of energy transfer from P-NCs to ML-MoSe₂ upon excitation. The lower efficiency of PL enhancement in ML-MoSe₂ indicates that only a fraction of the transferred energy results in the formation of excitons with the subsequent emission of photons. The calculated efficiencies should be in agreement for the exclusive process of radiative recombination of the transferred energy in the heterostructure. The observed discrepancy indicates additional processes. In fact, when consulting the energy level alignment, it becomes obvious that the energy transferred from P-NCs to ML-MoSe₂ would most likely populate the continuum states far above the excitonic levels in ML-MoSe₂, hence into the generation of free carriers. Given the low quantum efficiency of TMDC monolayers in general (<6%) due to defects, band nesting (at high

energy excitation),^[39] and exciton-exciton annihilation,^[40] we assume that only a fraction of those free carriers recombines radiatively, accounting for the 33% efficiency calculated above. To further evaluate this, we investigated the PL spectra of the ML-MoSe₂. In 2D-TMDCs it is very well established that enhanced carrier density can be extracted by closely examining and deconvoluting the PL spectra into the spectral contribution of exciton and trion PL.^[41] This is the result of the high binding energy of the trions (excitons that bind to a free carrier in the system) of >10 meV.^[41–44] Therefore the trion contribution can be an indicator for the free carrier density in the ML-MoSe₂ even at room temperature.^[41,45–49] The carrier density can be quantified by considering the thermal equilibrium between exciton (n_x), trion (n_T), and the free carrier density (n_e), which follows a Boltzmann distribution at low excitation densities.^[50,51] This model, based on the law of mass action, is given in Equation S4, Supporting Information.

Assuming that the relative masses and the trion binding energy remain unchanged upon the addition of P-NCs, we can obtain the change in the trion-exciton (n_T/n_x) density ratio from the ML-MoSe₂ PL alone and in the HET by deconvoluting the PL into two Gaussian curves (See Section 3 in Supporting Information). The higher energy peak corresponds to exciton (x_0) and the other to trion (x_T) PL (see Figure 3b, blue and orange curves, respectively). Since the intensity ratio (I_T/I_x) is proportional to the trion-exciton density (n_T/n_x) ratio, the increase in the free carrier density results in a higher (I_T/I_x).^[47] The co-existence of excitons, trions, and free carriers is typical for TMDCs. In fact, high excitation energies result into the generation of free carriers (electrons and holes), which bind to form excitons and other excitonic complex emissions, such as trions and biexcitons.^[52–55] Such high-energy excitation process can be considered analogous to the energy transfer to the exciton continuum observed by us. We substitute the density ratio with the intensity ratio of trion-exciton (values given in Table S4, Supporting Information) on both ML-MoSe₂ and HET and calculate a relative increase of up to 33% in the free carrier density in the HET (see Figure 3b and Section 3 in the Supporting Information for details).

We summarize our results in a one-particle energy level model shown in **Figure 4**. For pristine ML-MoSe₂, upon photoexcitation the dominant species found are excitons (left panel in Figure 4). With the addition of P-NCs, we see an increase of 33% in the overall emission obtained from the optical studies. Together with the low quantum yield of ML-MoSe₂, our results, therefore, suggest that the ET from P-NCs to ML-MoSe₂ results in an increased number of free carriers rather than tightly bound excitons. In photoexcited TMDCs, excitons and free carriers can co-exist.^[56] This increased free carrier density upon energy transfer is observed as an increased trion contribution to the spectrum (right panel in Figure 4). Hence, the route of energy transfer to the exciton continuum high above the excitonic states in the 2D-TMDC, represents an interesting route to generate directly free carriers in ML-MoSe₂. The additionally remaining energy that has been transferred but not detected by us, might be lost through other factors, such as the scattering of light from the top P-NCs layer.^[15]

As a proof of principle, we performed photocurrent measurements on ML-MoSe₂ and HET. An external bias is applied

Figure 4. Schematic one particle energy level model of the heterostructure. Left: one particle picture of ML-MoSe₂ alone depicting the energy levels of excitons (x_0) in the 1S and 2S states and the trions (x_T). The exciton continuum is given above. Right: illustration of the energy transfer process (ET) from the CsPbBr₃ NCs to ML-MoSe₂ with enhanced carriers in the exciton continuum and trion formation. DDAB ligands are depicted as grey energy levels between the two materials.

between the source-drain electrodes to observe the light-induced change in conductivity. The basic structure of the system is illustrated by the cross-sectional schematic diagram depicted in **Figure 5a** and the optical micrograph of the system is shown in Figure S5, Supporting Information. The current-voltage (I_{SD} - V_{SD}) curves of the HET system were investigated both in dark and under non-polarized white light illumination

(active area $\approx 500 \mu\text{m}^2$) at room temperature. The measurements were performed in a vacuum to avoid the influence of moisture and atmospheric gases and have been measured by varying V_{SD} up to 50 V. The comparison of the performance between ML-MoSe₂ and HET is described in Figure 5b. For both devices, I_{SD} is modulated by V_{SD} , both in dark and light conditions, indicating that I_{SD} can be effectively controlled by

Figure 5. a) Schematic illustration of the CsPbBr₃/MoSe₂ (HET) proof of concept device structure. b) Source-drain current (I_{SD}) versus source-drain voltage (V_{SD}), both in dark and under white light conditions at bias voltages between 0 and 50 V. c) Photocurrent response for white incident light power on the active area of the devices. The dashed lines represent a power-law fit to the data. d) Photoresponsivity versus the irradiance curves.

electrostatic doping. We observe that even in the dark the HET device outperforms the ML-MoSe₂ device by one order of magnitude (black curves in Figure 5b).

This can be explained by an improved transport of charges, induced by the contact of ML-MoSe₂ with the P-NCs. In general, current increase is attributed to an enhancement of the conductivity (defined as $\sigma \approx dI_{SD}/dV_{SD}$) due to the tuning of either mobility (μ_e) and/or carrier density n_e , as given by:^[57]

$$\Delta\sigma \sim \Delta n_e \cdot \mu_e \quad (5)$$

When the P-NCs get in touch with MoSe₂ it is conceivable that both μ_e and/or Δn_e are affected, as the interaction of the surface ligands of the P-NCs with ML-MoSe₂ might lead to the passivation of defects in the atomically thin 2D material, as shown also for other TMDC systems.^[58–61] In fact, the defect passivation can induce a twofold enhancement of mobility in TMDCs due to the lowering of scattering centers, with a consequent increase in Δn_e up to 40 times.^[58] While this can be an advantage for certain light-driven devices (e.g., solar cells), it might be detrimental for photodetector applications.

The I_{SD} – V_{SD} curves for both samples were measured also under optical power illumination ($P_{ex} = 252 \mu\text{W}$). Notably, the photocurrent (I_{ph}) of the HET, defined as the difference between the current under a white light stimulus and the dark current (I_{dark}), is one order of magnitude (from 219 nA to 1156 nA for $V_{SD} = 50 \text{ V}$, Figure 5b) higher than that of the pristine ML-MoSe₂ device. In dark conditions, the carriers are driven by an applied V_{SD} , hence a small I_{dark} flows across the device. Under light illumination, the absorbed photons generate electron-hole pairs that are separated and driven by the applied bias V_{SD} resulting in the observed photocurrent I_{ph} . We assume that the mobility μ_e of the channel material MoSe₂ in contact with the P-NCs is constant in dark and in light, as no chemical modification of the sample has been performed. Hence, the increase of σ is likely related to photogenerated excess carrier density Δn_e by one order of magnitude, giving another evidence of energy transfer from P-NCs. However, due to the complexity of analyzing optoelectronic systems, the exact quantification of the energy transfer process to the photocurrent generation is difficult, and we do not exclude a contribution also from the increased dark current. Subsequently, I_{ph} was measured under white light stimuli at different intensities over a range of optical powers from 10^{-5} to 10^{-4} W , as shown in Figure 5c. The presence of carrier generation, trapping, and recombination processes within the devices can be studied by the power dependence of the photodetector.^[62] In an ideal photodetector, the photocurrent I_{ph} is proportional to the incident light power ($I \approx P^\theta$, with the power exponent $\theta = 1$). However, by fitting the curve with the aforementioned power law, in both cases of ML-MoSe₂ and HET, we found $\theta = 0.59$ and $\theta = 0.38$, respectively. This deviation from the unity value typically arises from the distribution of traps and recombination centers within the bandgap^[63,64] and the saturation of these states under strong light excitation.^[62,65–67] In order to estimate the light-detection performance of the two systems, the photoresponsivity (R_{ph}), defined as the efficiency in converting the optical signal into an electrical one, represents a fundamental figure of merit. We calculated R_{ph} of both devices given by:^[62,65,68]

$$R_{ph} = \frac{I_{ph}}{I_r \cdot S} \quad (6)$$

in which I_r is the irradiance, S is the active area of the device. We found that the maximum measured responsivity for both devices is achieved at the lowest irradiance ($\approx 10 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$) for both the ML-MoSe₂ device ($R_{ph} \approx 9 \text{ A W}^{-1}$) and the HET device ($R_{ph} \approx 88 \text{ A W}^{-1}$) and decreases with the increase of irradiation. The calculated R_{ph} values for HET are about one order of magnitude higher compared to the ML-MoSe₂-based device. The reason why R_{ph} exponentially decreases with the laser power increase could be related to the scattering due to defects and related recombination processes.^[63,65,69,70] Taken all together, we were able to show that the HET device outperforms the ML-MoSe₂ device by one order of magnitude, hence exploiting the above-discussed effects related to the energy transfer.

3. Conclusion

To conclude, our HET of P-NCs/ML-MoSe₂ with a type I band alignment results into the efficient energy transfer from the nanocrystals to the MoSe₂. We observe the order of magnitude quenching of P-NC emission intensity and decay lifetime, and only minor enhancement in ML-MoSe₂ emission. We interpret these results as a direct energy transfer to the exciton continuum of MoSe₂ monolayers with the subsequent formation of free carriers and only a fraction recombining radiatively. We exploit this effect in a proof-of-concept heterostructure device, displaying order of magnitude enhancement of photocurrent. Taken together, in this work we identified a novel route to generate free carriers in MoSe₂ upon light absorption, avoiding the formation and subsequent dissociation of excitons with high binding energies in these materials. Hence, our results demonstrate new design opportunities for 2D-TMDC-based optoelectronic devices exploiting the direct generation of free carriers by energy transfer.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

energy transfer, excitons, free carrier generation, perovskite nanocrystals, transition metal dichalcogenides, triions

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Supporting Information

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Generation of Free Carriers in MoSe₂ Monolayers Via
Energy Transfer from CsPbBr₃ Nanocrystals

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Supporting Information

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1. Material fabrication and characterization methods

Synthesis of CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals: Perovskite nanocrystals were synthesized using the reported method.^[1,2] We adapted the halide hot injection method to produce CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals with oleic acid and a secondary alkyl amine, didodecylamine (DiDDAm) ligand and subsequently exchanged with didodecyldimethylammoniumbromide (DDAB, 98%) where all the chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. 20 mL of 1-octadecene (ODE, technical grade, 90%), 3 mL of oleic acid (OA, 90%), 156 mg of lead acetate trihydrate (PbAc₂·3H₂O, 99.99%), 34 mg of cesium carbonate (Cs₂CO₃, reagent Plus, 99%) were mixed in a 100mL 3-neck flask with a reflux condenser, a thermocouple probe and a magnetic stirrer. The solution was degassed under stirring at 115°C under vacuum for 30 min. 880 mg of didodecylamine (DiDDAm, 97%) were dissolved in 2 mL of toluene and taken in a 3 mL syringe in the glovebox. DiDDAm was injected into the cation precursor solution under nitrogen flow and the reaction mixture was kept at 115°C under stirring condition until the complete dissolution of the metal salt. Halide precursor solution 100 µL of benzoylbromide (97%) and 1 mL ODE was prepared in a glovebox while the cation reaction mixture is cooled down to 80°C. A yellow solution was formed after the swift injection of halide precursor into the cation reaction mixture. Reactions were stopped after 19s by lowering the temperature using a water-ice bath. Nanocrystals were separated and collected by centrifugation at 5000 rpm. The centrifugation were done twice to wring out the reaction mixture containing by-products (un-reacted reagents, excess of organic ligands) and the solvent (ODE). The collected particles were dispersed in toluene for ligand exchange.

Ligand exchange and purification: as synthesized nanocrystal (NC) ligands were exchanged to DDAB as ligand. 1 mL of DDAB (0.02M) was added to 4 mL of NC solution and stirred for 1

minute. 7.5 mL of ethyl acetate was added to the solution and centrifuged for 6 minutes at 6000 rpm. The supernatant was removed, while the precipitate was collected, well dried and dispersed in 5 mL toluene. The solution appeared turbid, and it has been centrifuged at 1500 rpm for 7 minutes to precipitate further non-soluble products. The supernatant was collected and purified via precipitation and redispersion process by adding ethyl acetate to NC solution (0.5:1 v/v) and centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 6 minutes. The precipitate has been collected and redispersed in 4 mL of dry toluene. The sample has been stored in air until used for our studies.

Fabrication of MoSe₂ monolayers: gold assisted mechanical exfoliation of MoSe₂ monolayers was carried out using a reported method.^[3-5] Due to the strong interaction between a clean gold surface and the top layer of TMDC, large flakes with high yield can be exfoliated from a flat TMDC crystal. (3-Aminopropyl)triethoxysilane (APTES) was deposited on Si/SiO₂ target substrate using atomic layer deposition (ALD) to produce a hydrophobic surface. Freshly evaporated gold (150 nm thick) was deposited on a thermal adhesive tape. This tape with the gold is used for the exfoliation of TMDC monolayer and transferred on a hydrophobic (APTES deposited) target substrate and the tape is released by heating to 125°C. All the polymers and organics were removed by placing the substrate (with monolayer and gold) firstly in boiling milliQ water (100°C) for 1h and then in boiling acetone (70°C) for 1 hour. The gold on top of the substrate is removed using gold etchant, solution of KI and I₂ (99.9%, Sigma Aldrich). Finally, the substrate with the TMDC monolayer is cleaned with milliQ water and rinsed using isopropanol. In order to avoid preparing fresh gold everytime, a protective layer of polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) can also be deposited on top to store the evaporated gold. APTES can also be deposited on target substrate by immersion in 2:100 (v/v) solution of APTES in milliQ water for 2h, followed by milliQ water rinse. The substrate must be treated previously with O₂ plasma to enhance the hydrophobization process.

Transmission Electron Microscopy: Bright-field TEM images of the NC samples were acquired by a JEOL JEM-1400Plus transmission electron microscope equipped with thermionic source (LaB6) operating at an acceleration voltage of 120 kV. The images were acquired by Gatan CCD camera Orius 830 (2048 × 2048 active pixels). Samples were prepared by drop-casting diluted solutions of NCs onto carbon film-coated 200 mesh copper grids for low-

resolution TEM. The size distribution dimension has been calculated on 400 nanocrystals (50 nanocrystals x 8 TEM images). The images were elaborated by ImageJ software.

Scanning Electron Microscopy: Helios Nanolab 650, FEI was used for imaging the nanocrystals and TMDC monolayers. No specific sample preparation was required for SEM imaging.

UV photolithography: Electrical contacts were fabricated by means of UV-photolithography. Sample with MoSe₂ flakes was spin coated (4000 rpm speed, 1000 rpm⁻¹ acceleration) with AZ5214E image reversal resist (MicroChemicals). After soft-baking at 110°C for 50 seconds, exposure of the contact pattern was performed with a mask aligner system. Image reversal was then obtained by baking at 120°C for 2 min and then performing a flood-exposure (without any mask) with the mask aligner (power intensity > 200 mJ/cm²). The resist was developed in AZ 726 MIF for 60 seconds, followed by deionized water rinse. Then a double layer composed of 5 nm Ti and 45 nm Au was evaporated by means of PVD evaporator. Eventually the sample was immersed in acetone overnight to complete the liftoff process.

Optical characterization:

Absorption spectra: The UV–visible absorption spectra of the monolayer film was recorded using a Varian Cary 5000 UV–vis absorption spectrophotometer. The NCs film has been obtained by spin coating the solution at 2000 rpm for 35 s onto a clean fused silica substrate (10x10 mm²). PL of the NCs film and PLQY of NC sample in solution has been measured using an Edinburgh FLS900 fluorescence spectrometer equipped with a xenon lamp and a monochromator. PLQY was measured using a calibrated integrating sphere ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 400 \text{ nm}$). The NC dispersion has been diluted in toluene to an optical density of 0.1 at the corresponding excitation wavelength to minimize reabsorption of the emitted light in quartz cuvettes with a path length of 1 cm.

Micro-photoluminescence: A 48.9 ps pulsed 400 nm Edinburgh laser (EPL-400) with tunable repetition rate (20 MHz – 1 KHz) used for excitation. The excitation laser was coupled into IX83 Olympus microscope and focused on the sample with 50X (N.A 0.8) microscope objective lens. The photo luminescence light was collected and collimated by the same objective lens, which was used for detection. The PL light was focused on slit of a Czerny-Turner HRS-500 spectrometer (Princeton Instruments) to resolve the light spectrally. The spectrally resolved light was detected and read using PIXIS CCD camera and Lightfield software (Princeton Instruments). For time-resolved PL, the PL light was detected using an avalanche photo-diode couple to PicoHarp 300 (PicoQuant) time correlated single photon counting (TCSPC) system.

Figure S1: (a) TEM image of CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals. (b) Histogram of the size distribution of CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals.

Figure S2: SEM image of 50 times dilute P-NC film spin-coated on Si/SiO₂ substrate.

Figure S3: Absorption spectrum of P-NC film of 50 times diluted solution

Figure S4: Box plot of maximum intensities from 10 different ML-MoSe₂ flakes before (TMD) and after the addition (HET) of P-NC.

Figure S5: Optical micrograph of the proof of concept device.

Table S1: Values used in the calculation of energy transfer efficiency from P-NC steady-state PL.

A_{HET}	A_{P-NC}	$A_{ML-MoSe_2}$	I_{P-NC}	I_{P-NC}^0
0.0481	0.0236	0.0245	$1.1656 \cdot 10^4$	$8.707 \cdot 10^4$

Table S2: Values used in the calculation of energy transfer efficiency from ML-MoSe₂ steady-state PL

A_{HET}	$A_{ML-MoSe_2}$	$I_{ML-MoSe_2}$	$I_{ML-MoSe_2}^0$
0.0337	0.0245	114093	126310

2. Exponential fit of PL decay:

The decay of the P-NC PL on the substrate was fitted with biexponential decay function (shown as equation S1), where $I(t)$ is the intensity at a given time, and τ_1 and τ_2 are the two time constants with amplitudes A_1 and A_2 respectively. The extracted values of the time constants and amplitudes are given in table 3. The equation used for amplitude average lifetime calculation is given in equation S2.^[6] The P-NC PL decay on the heterostructure was fitted with monoexponential function (equation S3) and the extracted are values are given in the main article.

$$I(t) = A_1 \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_1}\right) + A_2 \exp(-t/\tau_2) \quad S1$$

$$\tau_{avg} = \tau_{P-NC} = \frac{A_1 \tau_1^2 + A_2 \tau_2^2}{A_1 \tau_1 + A_2 \tau_2} \quad S2$$

$$I(t) = A \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_{HET}}\right) \quad S3$$

Table S3: The extracted amplitudes and time constants on P-NC PL decay on the substrate.

A_1	A_2	τ_1	τ_2
0.51	0.49	1.23 ns	3.45 ns

3. Model and the deconvolution of MoSe₂ PL:

The carrier density in thermal equilibrium between exciton (n_X), trion (n_T) and the free carrier density (n_e), that follows a Boltzmann distribution at low excitation densities is given in equation S4, where m_X , m_T and m_e are relative masses of exciton, trion and free electron respectively, and E_B is the trion binding energy.^[7,8]

$$\frac{n_X n_e}{n_T} = \frac{4m_X m_e}{\pi h^2 m_T} \cdot k_B T \exp\left(-\frac{E_B}{k_B T}\right) \quad (S4)$$

The MoSe₂ PL were fitted with two Gaussians, which corresponds to exciton and trion shown in equation S5, where I_X , I_T , W_X , W_T , λ_X and λ_T are intensity of exciton, trion, bandwidth of exciton, trion and peak wavelength of exciton and trion respectively. The width of the Gaussian for exciton (same for trion) and the data range were kept constant for both pristine MoSe₂ and HET to extract the intensities of exciton and trion (shown in table S4). Since intensities of exciton (I_X) and trion (I_T) are directly proportional to the densities of exciton (n_X) and trion (n_T), we can obtain the ratio of these densities from the intensities.^[9–12]

$$I = I_0 + \frac{I_X}{W_X \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}}} e^{-\frac{2}{W_X^2}(\lambda - \lambda_X)^2} + \frac{I_T}{W_T \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}}} e^{-\frac{2}{W_T^2}(\lambda - \lambda_T)^2} \quad \text{S5}$$

Table S4: Exciton and trion intensities obtained from the deconvolution of ML-MoSe₂ PL.

I_X MoSe ₂	I_T MoSe ₂	I_X HET	I_T HET
13049	9823	12927	12925

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